

THE MAIN CONTRIBUTION OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG 'S WORK TO UZBEK LITERATURE

Gulomova Shakhzoda Khabibulla qizi

UzSWLU, 3rd year student

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Annotation: This article discusses one of the outgoing writer Alexander Feinberg's work and his masterpiece in literature. The author of the article analyzed his work and gave his idea about Alexander Feinberg's very works.

Key words: publish, prominent, figure, aesthetic domain, poetry, scripts, lyrical, epic, collection, animated films, literature, rhythm, achievement, method, approach, create.

As the Prezident of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.Mirziyoyev mentioned : Literature is the heart of the nation; It reflects the spirituality of the nation. In today's difficult times, it is necessary to find a way to the heart of a person , to make effective use of the influence of literature, and to direct it towards noble goals. We create, we study the legacy of our great ancestors; all the conditions have been created to create a great literature worthy of our culture.

Alexander Feinberg was the writer and poet, he had warm thoughts about Uzbeks, strong, powerful love and respect to Uzbekistan and loyalty to their homeland. Because of his strong love and talent of the great poet for literature and poetry, literature was considered an integral part of his life. He increased his passion for learning and literature in order to become knowledgeable and have bright future. Moreover, Alexander Feinberg studied poetic and artistic works with a serious approach to the creativity of Uzbeks. He contributed to the wide spread of Uzbek poets by translating their poetic works. A lot of poetic and epic works of Alisher Navoiy was translated by Alexander Feinberg. For example, O'tkir Hashimov's "Rebellion of Spirits" and Abdulla Oripov's poetry collections whereby. Abdullah Qahhor said "The more talented the writer, the more experienced the penman, the more the people will be grateful to him, the more he will respect his work and literature in general." National poet of Uzbekistan A. Aripov thanks A. Feinberg for his respect for the Uzbek people and their culture, for his loyalty to the invincible cheerful spirit of Afandi in his satirical poem "The String of the Rubayat", and in another cited article "My countryman" calls him "not a slogan internationalist" , but a "real countryman" . M.Muhammad Dost and J.Kasimov, a cinematographer, say about Alexander Feinberg's filmography: " It is imperative to strive to be a controller of artistic reality. He used to be like that, but today just a few people are like that.

However, many people say that "Feinberg was an ordinary man...", he allowed himself to be different without wearing a mask. It is absolutely true that his works irreplaceable. Also, Feinberg's great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature was appreciated by our government, and the honorary titles of "Honored Cultural Worker of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" were awarded as a sign of our boundless respect for this great man.

Let's discuss his poems in this article. In his poems we can see love, belief, missing, looking forward to someone. Besides that, we can see that he applauds his mother as the person who misses him a lot and waits for him all the time. Furthermore, he tries to express his love to her with this line of beautiful words. Therefore, in 1965 "Velotracks" and then "Etude" (1967), "Seconds" (1969), "Poems" (1977), "Far Bridges" (1978), "Answer" (1982), "Short wave" (1983), "Spread string" (1984), "Liberal sonnets" (1990), "Sheet" (2008). His poems are: "Change", "Youth", "New world", "Eastern Star", "New Volga", "Etude", "Second", "Poems", "Far Bridges", "Answer", "Short Wave", "Spreading net", "Free Sonnets" and so on. Besides that, he has made seven feature films at the Uzbek film studio: "Stadium in the Sky", "Under the Hot Sun", "My brother", "Healed in Kandahar" and "Criminals and Justified" at the Tajik film studio. The film which was named "Stadium in the Sky" based on his storyline, was produced in 1999. But the lyrics for the film were written by Alexander Feinberg in 1979.

The Giant and the Short was his first full-length film, chosen topic's applicability, eternity, and profundity have greatly contributed to an uninhibited great sense of humor. As it seems authors' poetry constantly filled with people and the majority of his work extensive, vivacious and multifaceted. One can see wide range of topics, philosophy, complexity, and is found to be predictive.

However, A. Feinberg said that he had happiness on his head, the reason because of it he lived in the independent country of Uzbekistan. So many Uzbek writers, artists, musicians, composers, poets and other professionals helped him and have been friendly. They shared, discussed, and make a speech in the field of literature. He also considered himself as a child of Uzbekistan and was proud to live in this nation. Undoubtedly, he became one of the brightest stars in the sky of Uzbek poetry. His works are deeply rooted to the literary lovers. Alexander Feinberg was awarded the title of People's Poet of Uzbekistan by our First President I. Karimov. Besides that, He was awarded the "Pushkin Medal" in 2008 by the decree of the President of Russia for his great contribution to the strengthening of cultural ties between the Uzbek and Russian nations.

As a conclusion, A. Fineberg is a person who always encourages everyone to read, listen, listen and think, be astonished, mock, and think, poets can be challenging to write about. After reading some of Alexander Feinberg's final poems repeatedly, one can sit and reflect about him. And just thinking about it makes someone happy, inspires them to live, and makes them proud of their land and nation. In addition to, Feinberg's poems, you will learn a lot of new things, not about him, but about yourself, and only about yourself, because Alexander Feinberg's poems are so immeasurable.

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